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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in our contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

AN ANALYSIS OF THE ISLAMIC SYSTEM OF ELECTING LEADERS AS AN ALTERNATIVE TO CONSTITUTIONAL DEMOCRACY

By

Babayo Yakubu¹

Abstract

In both the Islamic Legal System and the Secular Legal Systems, leadership is of paramount importance. Therefore, where a particular Nation is having failure in the most important aspect of its existence (leadership) the most sensible route for such a Country is to look at other Countries or systems that are considered successful to improve itself and make sure it survives and develops. The problem-solving approach in Comparative Law asks the question, how a specific social or legal problem is encountered and resolved in both society A and society B? Which legal or other institutions cope with this problem? Comparative Law system seek out a social problem or need in one society, discover the institution that deals with it and then looks to other societies for institutions, legal or otherwise, which deal with the same problem and copy the process of dealing with such problem. Muslims all over the world with the understanding of the religion believe that the era of the Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.) and his orthodox successors were the best era in the history. The Prophet (S.A.W.) and the four rightly guided successors were the best rulers. Therefore, to the majority of Muslims, the Governmental System of the Prophet (S.A.W.) and his Successors is the best system of Government. However, many do not understand what constituted the System of Governance under Islamic Legal System? How does the system provide for electing leaders as found under the various systems of the modern countries? With these questions in mind, this paper aims to analyses the Islamic system of governance and how it differed with the other system of Governance, with the objective of discussing the process of electing leaders under the Islamic Legal System. In order to achieve this, the research used doctrinal method and analyses some Qur'anic verses as well as the Hadith of the Prophet (S.A.W.) and the Ijma of the companions. Findings and recommendations forms the concluding part of the paper.

Keywords: Islamic Law, Politics, Leadership, Democracy, Shura, Bay'ah

¹ Lecturer I, Department of Islamic Law, Sa'adu Zungur University. G.S.M. +2348039647387 Email: yakubumisau1031@gmail.com

1.0 Introduction

Countries of the modern world are guided by Legal Systems, which define the political set-up and the way and manner the country will be governed, providing how resources are to be shared and how leaders are to be chosen. Politics is seen as a science dealing with the form, organisation, administration of a state and a State is described as a body politic organised for supreme civil rule and government.² Democracy, as a system of government becomes the most popular system of the modern world. Underdeveloped Countries are often pressured into adopting democracy by the developed countries. Countries that adopt other system of government are frowned at and regarded as undemocratic and backward. Countries that are inclined towards Islamic legal system are viewed as having a system that is not compatible with Democracy. The countries that are considered as the world major powers, insisted that every other country must adopt democracy as their system of government.³

The Islamic Legal System as one of the world major legal systems is all encompassing. It provides for all aspect of human lives. Islamic Legal System teaches its followers almost everything, from worshipping, table manners, to toilet manners and to the minute details of how to live with one another in a family setup and society at large. The Qur'an provides everything that nothing is left out from the book.⁴ The Muslims believed that Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.) was chosen to be the leader of the whole mankind. He is the messenger of Allah and his main duty was to guide the whole world to the right path through what was revealed to him from Allah. The Qur'an commands us to obey the messenger; "...and obey Allah and the messenger..."⁵ This automatically makes the Prophet a leader. However, there is no specific form of government prescribed by the Qur'an and the Sunnah. No detailed blueprints for the form of government are given,⁶ as obtainable in the modern countries of the world. Therefore, what constitutes the System of Governance under Islamic Legal System? How does the

² Mohammad M., *Islam and its Political System* (International Islamic Publishers (New Delhi) 1992) p. 7

³ Kirman J, S. *Islam, Politics and Governance Totalitarian Movements and Political Religions*, (2008) Vol.9, No.1, 43-59.

⁴ *Qur'an: al-An'am* verse 38.

⁵ *Qur'an: al-Ma'idah* verse 92.

⁶ Mohammad M. op cit p. 42

system provide for electing leaders as found under the various systems of the modern countries?

1.2. Islamic System of Governance

Muslims all over the world with the understanding of the religion believe that the era of the Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.) and his orthodox successors were the best era in history. The Prophet (S.A.W.) and the four rightly guided successors were the best rulers. Therefore, to the majority of Muslims, the Governmental System of the Prophet (S.A.W.) and his Successors is the best system of Government. However, the exact nature of the system of government is not understood by many. To understand the Governmental System of the Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.), the best approach is to study it in the light of the theories of State which are known in the field of modern Constitutional Law.⁷ Islamic Constitutional Law writers believed that the system of governance immediately after the Prophet (S.A.W.) was the institution of the Caliphate (*Khilafah*).⁸ Caliph (*Khalifah*) means one who occupies the place of someone in his absence. More specifically Caliph refers to the role of the leader as the follower of the traditions of the Prophet (S.A.W.) in conducting the affairs of the community.⁹

Abu al-Hassan al-Mawardi, the celebrated Shafi'i jurist in his authoritative exposition of the ideal theory of the Caliphate, "*Ahkam al-Sultaniyah*" defined the Caliphate as the succession to the leadership of the holy Prophet after his death for the preservation of the faith and guiding the worldly affairs of muslims. To him, the obligation of instituting the Caliphate was founded in revelation rather than in reason as generally argued. This was supported by the consensus (*Ijma*) of the companion of the Prophet (S.A.W.)¹⁰

The Caliphate as an Islamic System of Governance differs from most common systems of Governance today in its spirit and mostly in its shape. The shape of the Caliphate system is not monarchical in nature. In the monarchical system, the king assumes leadership through inheritance without the citizens having any say in it,

⁷ Hashim Y. A. op cit p.2

⁸ Muhammed S.E. On the Political System of the Islamic State (American Trust Publications, Indiana, 1980) P.64

⁹ Ahmed M. Islamic Political System in the Modern Age: Theory & Practice (Adam Publishers & Distributors. New Delhi, 2007) p.108

¹⁰ Ibid p.122

whereas in the caliphate system of governance, the method of appointing a Caliph (Leader) is through the principles of *Shura* (Consultation) and *Bay'ah* (Pledge of Allegiance). The monarchical system allows the monarch special privileges and rights exclusive to him which places him above the law. In contrast, the leader under Caliphate system does not enjoy any special privileges over his citizens. The *Ummah* selects him and gives him the pledge of allegiance willingly so as to implement the Laws of Allah. He is restricted in all of his actions, judgments and in looking after the interests and affairs of the *Ummah* by the divine rules.¹¹ The Caliphate system differs from other system of governance all over the world. The shape of the Caliphate is not Imperial in nature, and is completely inconsistent with imperialism. The imperial system does not treat the regions of different races and nationalities equally. Instead, it gives privileges, in ruling, finance and the economy to the center of the empire. The Islamic way of ruling aims to create equality between citizens in all regions of the state, therefore rejecting tribalism. This is in contrast with Imperial states where colonies were created and exploited to enrich the imperial power base centrally.¹²

The Caliphate system is not federal where there are autonomous regions and unity only in general ruling. It is rather a system of unity, where all the units are considered equal. The finance of all the regions will be the same, as will their budget. The Islamic System of Governance is not republican. The republican system emerged as a reaction to the tyranny of monarchies, where Kings govern their countries and people as they wish. So a king would implement laws as he liked. The republican system attempted to transfer sovereignty and authority to the people through democracy. There are also cases where authority was handed over to a first minister and his cabinet in some monarchies in which case the King or Queen becomes a figurehead only. Islamic System of Governance is distinct from all these systems. In the Islamic System, the right of legislation is not for the people.¹³ The system of Governance under Islamic Law has a major difference with democratic system of Governance in terms of giving the right of legislation to the people, democratic system is not committed to divine rules at all and instead taking freedom as its core principle. Democracy is beyond a means

¹¹ Tahrir H. "The Institutions of State in the *Khilafah* (Ruling and Administration) (Darul-Ummah Beirut-Lebanon, 2005) p.15

¹² Ibid

¹³ Ibid p.15

for electing the ruler. It always sees itself as been secular and opposes any adoption of State religion.¹⁴

Before the advent of the Islamic State in *Madina*, Law, in other societies at the time, was the will of a dictator or powerful personalities in the society. Ancient civilizations such as Egypt, Persia and the Roman Empire were few examples in that regard. As such, the evolution of Islamic State based on “rule of law” was a great step in emergence of the modern concept of State. The companions understood the difference between the Islamic State and other forms of political systems. The title the Companions used in addressing the office of the successor to the Prophet; “*Khilafat Rasulallah*” that is “Successor to the Prophet” was intended to emphasize the need and requirement of following the guidance of the Prophet (S.A.W.) and maintaining the continuity of his message. It is also an indication that the Calipha is only to implement the Law as it is not as he wishes, unlike Kings or Emperors.¹⁵ God’s laws, expressed in the *Shari’ah* provide the only adequate limitation to fallible human authorities. Of all the systems of government in the world, only the caliphate acknowledged the sovereignty of God’s law. The caliphate is also the only institution required for establishing a rule of law that protects citizens from the arbitrary whims and abuses of their rulers, for the caliphate, of all the world’s systems of government, was the only system charged with enforcing Islamic Law.¹⁶

Under the institution of Caliphate (Islamic system of Governance), the title given to the leader could be the *Khalifah*, the *Imam* or the *Amir al-Mu’minin* as narrated in a sound hadith of the prophet and in the *Ijma* of the *Sahabah* (consensus of the companions). The *Khulafa Al-Rashidin* (first four Prophet’s successors) held such titles. Abu Said Al-Khudri reported that the Messenger of Allah said: If the pledge of allegiance (*Bay’ah*) has been taken for two *Khulafa* kill the later of them. Abdullah ibn Amr Ibn al-‘Aas reported from the Prophet (S.A.W.) that Whoever pledge allegiance to an *Imam* giving him the clasp of his hand and the fruit of his heart shall obey him as long as he can.¹⁷ In another report, Auf Ibn Malik reported the saying of the Prophet

¹⁴ Ibid p.17

¹⁵ Muhammed S.E. op cit p.1

¹⁶ James B. “The Controversy of Shaykh 'Ali 'Abd Al-Raziq” (Unpublished Dissertation Submitted to the Department of Religion In Partial Fulfillment for PhD Requirements, Florida State University Libraries, 2012) p. 1

¹⁷ Tahrir H. op cit p.8

(S.A.W.) that The best of your *Imams* (Leaders) are those whom you love and they love you and who pray for you and you pray for them...¹⁸ When Abu Bakr heard himself addressed as ‘God’s Deputy,’ he responded, ‘I am not God’s Deputy (*Khalifat Allah*), but the Successor of God’s Messenger (*Khalifat rasul Allah*).¹⁹ In another report, *Umayyad* caliph al-Walid II (d.744) described the leadership responsibilities in his letter of succession. He divided leaders in Islamic history into the era of the Prophets, ending with Prophet Muhammad’s death, and the age of the caliphs who have inherited the Prophets’ authority.²⁰

In the above traditions, the title of the ruler under Islamic system of governance can be either caliph or the *Imam*. As for the title of *Amir al-Mu’minin*, it came from a report that Umar ibn al-Khattab had visitors from *Iraq* and asked for permission to see *Amir al-Mu’minin* (the leader of the believers). Since then, they started using this title in writing. Consequently, the Muslims continued to call the *Khulafa* after ‘Umar by this title.²¹

1.3 The Process of Electing Leaders in Islamic Law

It is an established fact that the Prophet did not expressly anoint anyone to succeed him nor expressly lay down any rule or conduct to be followed in appointing his successor to conduct the affairs of the Islamic state. What the Prophet left behind for the companions to follow was the manner of his living among the Muslims through which the general principles that a ruler must abide has become clear. Furthermore, through the actions and utterances of the Prophet, the ideals to be upheld and maintained by both the ruler and the subject were established.²²

This openness with regards to the election of leaders follows the nature of all other Islamic legislations in which there is elements of flexibility and a room for human contributions. This will allow the possibility of continually building the system. Furthermore, without setting a certain conduct to be followed, the Prophet allows generation of Muslims in different parts of the world to decide how to choose their

¹⁸ Ibid

¹⁹ James B. op cit p.29

²⁰ Ibid

²¹ Ibid p.9

²² Muhammed S.E. op cit p.27

leaders according to their interest and the requirements of time, place and changing circumstances, provided they will abide by the general rules of Islamic law in regard to consultation, justice and equality. There is a belief that it was a deliberate act on the part of the Prophet to leave the matter to consultation among Muslims so that they are bound only by that which served their interest through the ages.²³

When the Prophet's cousin and son-in-law, Ali (RA) asked him how Muslims were to decide, after his demise, on matters that has no clear direction in either the *Qur'an* nor the *Sunnah*, he advised that they should not make decisions on the basis of a single opinion but after due consultation (*Shura*) among his trusted followers.²⁴ In keeping this advice, the companions when they assumed the caliphate consulted each other on issues such as war against apostates and appropriate penalty for alcohol consumption. Umar was known to have regularly resorted to *Shura*. As an example, he consulted the *Muhajirun* and *Ansar* about the plague that had broken out in Syria. Umar appointed a committee for the purpose of electing one among them as his successor on the basis of *Shura*.²⁵ The concept of *Shura* found its ground in the holy Qur'an: *Consult them in the matter*. It is a formula in Islamic jurisprudence (*Usul fiqh*) that "Command indicates obligation" and the above cited verse is in command voice, that means it is obligatory on the Head of State to consult, and as the verse addressed one person, the conclusion should be that person is the head of state.²⁶

Another verse on *Shura* is the one that says: *Those who responded to their God (obeying Allah), perform prayers; their affairs are conducted by Shura and paid zakat*. This verse, unlike the first one, referred to many people, and the conclusion here is that, when there is no head of state at the time, the consultation (*Shura*) should be among the people. However, where there is head of state, then the consultation should be done by the head of state as stated above. Another point is the way the verse mentioned obligatory acts together with consultation, that is obeying Allah, performing *Salah*, and paying *Zakat* are all obligatory acts in Islam, and so, mentioning all of them in the same breath with consultation indicates that

²³ Ibid

²⁴ Mahmud al-Alusi S.A. *Ruh al-Ma'ani fi al-Qur'an al'Azim wa al-sab al-Mathani (Dar Ihya al-Turath al-Arabi*, Beirut) p.24, Dangor S. *Shura, Democracy and the Muslim World (American Muslim (Tam) 2002)* available @ <https://www.theamericanmuslim.org> accessed on 26th May, 2024 p 7

²⁵ Ibid

²⁶ Dangor S. p.12

consultation too is an obligatory act.²⁷ Abu-Hurairah was reported to have said that: I have never seen anyone who always consults his companions other than the prophet. The Prophet was reported to have said to Abu Bakr and Umar that If you two agreed on a certain matter in consultation, I would not disagree with both of you. It was reported by Hassanul Basri that the Messenger of Allah used to consult even women and considered their advice.²⁸

The companions continued with this trend of the Prophet by consulting one another. After the demise of the Messenger of Allah, the appointment of *Abu-Bakr (R.A)* as the first caliph was one of the best examples of *Shura* by the companions of the Prophet, that is the meeting of *Sakifah bani Sa'idah* where they were in consultation for 3 days. Another authority from the *Ijma* of the companions on *Shura* was the issue of refusal to give *zakat* by some Muslims during Abu-Bakr the first Caliph. After consultation with the companions over the issue, he decided to fight them. Even though most of the companions advised against it, the fact remains that he consulted the companions.²⁹ During the time of Umar the second Caliph after the conquest of *Iraq*, there were spoils of war in terms of vast land, and caliph Umar consulted other companions on what to do with the land³⁰. From these instances, it is clear that *Shura* has been the modus operandi in the Islamic system of Government. The fact that the first four successors of the Prophet emulated him in respect of consulting knowledgeable and wise companions is well established. It could be said that *Shura* was established as a fundamental principle of governance in Islam by the Prophet and his first four successors. The Caliph was to establish a consultative council (*Majlis al-Shura*), rule in consultation with this council and administer the affairs of state with their consent.³¹

Shura means a serious and effective participation in making a decision, not merely a ceremonial procedure. The Quran addresses the Prophet who received divine revelation to rely on *Shura* in making decisions concerning common matters for which

²⁷ Mohamad, Z. "Principles of Government in Islam" (Unpublished Manuscript, International Islamic University, Malaysia. 2015) p. 8

²⁸ Musnad Imam Ahmad

²⁹ Dangor S. p.18

³⁰ Ibid p. 15

³¹ Muhammed, S.E. op cit p.26

no specific revelation had come. ... *and take counsel with them in all matters of common concern; then, when you have made a decision (accordingly), place your trust in God.* If the prophet is addressed to involve the believers in decision-making regarding a common matter for which no specific revelation exists, all the believers must follow this teaching. The distinguished Andalusian Qur'anic commentator *Ibn 'Atiyya* stated in his commentary on this verse: “*Shura* is one of the basics of Islamic law (*Shari'ah*), and a mandatory rule; and anyone [who is entrusted with a public authority] who does not take the counsel of those who have knowledge and are conscious of God, should be dismissed from the position, and there is no argument about that.”³²

The other major principle apart from *Shura* when it comes to electing leaders under the Islamic System of Governance is *Bay'ah*. This can be seen right from the *Bay'ah* given by the Muslims to the Prophet and from the Prophet's directives that the *Ummah* should pledge *Bay'ah* to their Leaders. Furthermore, it is said that the *Bay'ah* given to the Prophet was not on Prophethood, it was on a *Bay'ah* over ruling, for it was regarding action not belief. Therefore, the allegiance was given to him as a ruler, and not as a Prophet or a Messenger. This is because acknowledging the Prophethood is linked to belief (*Iman*). Hence the *Bay'ah* to him was only in his capacity as the head of the state.³³

The *Bay'ah*, like *Shura* also has its basis in the Qur'an and Hadith. It is stated in the Qur'an: O Prophet! If the believers come to you to take the oath (*Bay'ah*) that they will not associate [in worship] anything with Allah, that they will not steal, that they will not commit adultery, that they will not kill their children, that they will not utter slander, intentionally forging falsehood, and they will not disobey you in any just matter (*Ma'roof*), then receive their oath (*Bay'ah*). In another verse, it is stated that: “Verily those who pledge their allegiance to you do no less than pledge their allegiance to Allah: The Hand of Allah is over their hands.”³⁴ Authorities from the *Sunnah* includes reports that *Bukhari* narrated from *Ubadah bin al-Samit* who said; “We have pledged allegiance to the Messenger of Allah to listen and obey in ease and in hardship

³² Osman F. “Islam in a modern state: Democracy and the concept of *Shura* (*Occasional paper series*, 2001) available @ <http://www.paperbackswap.com/islam-modern-state-fathi-os>. Accessed on 25th May, 2024

³³ Ibid p.29

³⁴ Ibid p.31

and that we do not dispute the matter (authority) with its people and that we stand for and speak the truth wherever we are and that in the service of Allah we would fear the blame of no one.”³⁵ In another tradition, the Messenger of Allah said: “Whosoever pledges allegiance (*Bay’ah*) to an *Imam* by giving him the clasp of his hand, let him obey him if he is able to do so, but if another comes along to dispute with him, then kill the latter.” Also, the Prophet was reported to have said: “If two *Khulafa* were pledged allegiance (*Bay’ah*), then kill the latter of them.”³⁶

In another report *Abu Hurairah*, the Prophet’s saying: “Banu Israel used to be governed by Prophet, every time a Prophet died, another came after him, and there is no Prophet after me. There will be *Khulafa* and there will be many.” They asked the Prophet on what to do He answered that they should fulfil the *Bay’ah* to them one after the other, and give them their due right, surely Allah will hold them accountable.³⁷ These texts (*Nafs*) of the primary sources of Islamic Law explicitly show the necessity of *Bay’ah* in appointing a Calipha. This was understood and practiced by all of the *Sahabah (Ijma)*. The *Bay’ah* given to the rightly guided Caliphs was clear in this regard.³⁸

1.3.1 The Meeting of *Saqifah Bani Sa’idah* (A Meeting Place in *Madina*)

The death of the Prophet threw the Companions into state of fear and uncertainty. The Prophet always took responsibility of the political affairs of the Islamic state and always provided answers to all the questions. Now the Prophet is gone and immediately the people of *Madina* meet at a place called *Saqifah bani Sa’idah* discussing the question of who will succeed the Prophet. At the time the Prophet was not even buried. There must be someone to stir the affairs of the Islamic state. Abubakar Sadiq, the closest friend to the Prophet was informed about the meeting and immediately went there with Umar bin Khattab and Abu Ubaida ibn Jarrah. The *Ansar* (people of *Madina*) were claiming to be the rightful people to produce the successor to

³⁵ Ibid

³⁶ Ibid

³⁷ Tahrir H. p.32

³⁸ Ibid

the Prophet. Their claim was based on the fact that they were the ones that offered help to the Prophet and defended Islam with their persons and their properties.³⁹

However, Abubakar was of the opinion that the *Muhajirun* (the immigrants) were the best to produce the successor to the Prophet. He commended all the merits they mentioned and agreed with them on all the merits. However, he pointed out that such merits must not be the only consideration and does not give the right to the caliphate to the exclusion of all others. He further pointed out that the *Muhajiruns* were first to accept Islam, the first to worship Allah, they were from the same clan with the Prophet, suffered all adversities and injuries together with the Prophet. Abubakar further clarified that the rest of the Arabs can only recognize authority from the *Quraish* clan. To strengthen his argument, Abubakar cited the Prophet saying that *Quraish* were the leading examples. *Sa'ad bin Ubaida* from the *Ansar* confirmed this saying of the Prophet. Another *Ansar* leader, *Hubab bin Mundhir* suggested that two rulers should be selected each from the *Ansar* and the *Muhajirun* which was swiftly dismissed.⁴⁰

Following further deliberation and consultation, Umar bin Khattab and Abu Ubaida ibn Jarrah sworn an allegiance to Abu Bakr. Among his reasons in pledging his allegiance to Abu Bakr, Umar stated that Abubakar was the virtuous among all the Muslims and that the Prophet appointed him to lead prayers, which is the most important act in Islam. Above all, the Qur'an mentioned Abu Bakr as the second of the two, the first being the Prophet, the *Shura* at the *Saqifah* settled on Abu Bakr and gave him *Bay'ah* there and then. The following day, the rest of the Muslim *Ummah* paid tributes and pledged their allegiances to Abubakar as the Calipha (the leader of Islamic state) and the successor to the Prophet.⁴¹ The meeting of *Saqifah Bani Sa'idah* marked the beginning and the emergence of the caliphate, a system which became the hallmark of the Governmental organization of the Islamic State. This system continues in one form or another up to the twentieth century when the system of caliphate was abolished with the headquarters at the time in Turkey.⁴²

³⁹ Muhammed, S, E, p.30

⁴⁰ Ibid

⁴¹ Ibid

⁴² Ibid. p.31

This meeting was purely conducted through the principle of *Shura* as commanded by the Qur'an. Abu Bakr, the first Caliph was appointed by *Shura* and his appointment was confirmed by *Bay'ah*. Abubakar then became the first Caliph after the Prophet and continued with the expansion of the Islamic State, thus formalizing the system of *Shura* as the means of running his Government. He always consult (*Shura*) other companions in almost every decision. When it dawned on him that he may not survive his illness, and the Muslim armies were fighting the Persian and Roman superpowers of that time, he felt it necessary to engage in *Shura* (consultation) with other companions as regards to his successor. He continued consulting the companions for three months, and thereafter announced the nomination of Umar to succeed him. It was after the death of Abu Bakr that Muslims came to the *Masjid* and pledged their allegiance (*Bay'ah*) to 'Umar through which Umar became the Calipha for the Muslims. Thus the second Calipha was nominated by Abu Bakr after *Shura* and his appointment was confirmed by the *Bay'ah* of the Muslims.⁴³ Umar, the second Caliph gave so much attention to the institution of *Shura* to the extent that at the point of his death he inaugurated a *Shura* council consisting of seven companions whom were promised paradise in their life time, with the term of reference of appointing his successor. *Abdul-Rahman ibn 'Awf* then asked the six whether any of them can voluntarily withdraw his candidature, as none of them volunteer, he said, "I myself renounce my right to the *Khilafah*." Then he started to consult them one by one. He would ask them, "Apart from yourself, who do you think is worthy of this authority from among this group?" Their answer was confined to two: Ali and Uthman. Then *Abdul-Rahman* sought the opinion of the Muslims regarding the two people whom they would elect as Calipha. He set out to gauge who the Muslims in *Madinah* thought should be nominated for the post of Calipha and visited many houses in that process. He asked the men and women who they would select until he concluded that the overall consensus was in favour of 'Uthman. 'Uthman was then given the pledge (*bay'ah*).⁴⁴ At the time of Uthman's murder the Muslim masses of *al-Madinah* and *al-*

⁴³ Al-Maududi S.A. "The Islamic Law and Constitution" (Islamic Publications Ltd, Lahore, 1975) 5th ed. p.218

⁴⁴ Ibid

Kufah gave the *bay'ah* to Ali ibn Abi Talib, so he became the Calipha by the *bay'ah* of the Muslims.⁴⁵

1.4 Conclusion

From the analysis above, the paper made the following findings:

- i. System of governance under Islamic Law was that of Caliphate system which was developed with the advent of the Islamic State of *Madina* after the demise of the Prophet with Abu Bakr as the first Calipha followed by Umar, Uthman and Ali collectively referred to as the Rightly Guided Caliphs.
- ii. The process of nominating and subsequent election of leaders under the Caliphate System can either come directly from consultation (*Shura*) and confirmed by pledge of allegiance (*Bay'ah*) as in the case of Abu Bakr's election, or through nomination by the incumbent leader after consultation (*Shura*) and confirmation by the *Ummah* after the death of the incumbent leader (*Bay'ah*) as in the case of Umar's election. It can also be by a Consultative Forum (*Majlis Shura*) and assented by the *Ummah* through *Bay'ah* as in the case of Uthman's election.
- iii. The voting rights in the Election of Leaders under Islamic System of Caliphate were confined to educated and influential people in the society.

From the above findings, the paper made the following recommendations:

- i. Any Country with dominant Muslim population should adopt the Caliphate System as its System of Governance as it is less expensive and very difficult to be penetrated by corruption and the system was proved to be a very successful one.
- ii. The Principles of *Shura* can be adopted by Muslims in their day-to-day activities as it proved to be an efficient method of solving problems and it creates a sense of inclusiveness in any given environment.

Other system of Governance such as democratic system can adopt the Islamic System of electing leaders whereby only educated and influential members of the society will

⁴⁵ Ibid p. 219

be eligible to vote to have the possibility of having the best leaders and not the general public having the same right of voting.